

МІНІСТЕРСТВО ОХОРОНИ ЗДОРОВ'Я УКРАЇНИ
Харківський національний медичний університет

Громадське здоров'я в Україні: Проблеми та способи їх вирішення

Томілінські читання

*Матеріали VI науково-практичної конференції
з міжнародною участю, присвяченої 100-річному ювілею
кафедри громадського здоров'я та управління охороною здоров'я
Харківського національного медичного університету*

м. Харків, 02 листопада 2023 року

Харків
ХНМУ
2023

УДК 614.2(477)
Г87

Затверджено Вченою радою ХНМУ.
Протокол № 11 від 23.11.2023 р.

Редакційна колегія: М'ясоєдов В.В., Огнев В.А., Нестеренко В.Г.,
Сокол К.М., Мельниченко О.А., Подпрядова А.А.

Г87 **Громадське здоров'я в Україні: проблеми та способи їх вирішення «Томілінські читання»:** матеріали VI науково-практичної конференції з міжнародною участю присвяченої 100-річному ювілею кафедри громадського здоров'я та управління охороною здоров'я Харківського національного медичного університету, Харків, 02 листопада 2023 р. / ред. кол.: В.В. М'ясоєдов, В.А. Огнев, В.Г. Нестеренко та ін. Харків, 2023. – 228 с.

УДК 614.2(477)

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– facilitating the implementation of the regional implementation strategy thanks to regional cooperation.

The Madrid Plan is not a binding document, it calls for a change in attitudes, policies and practices so that older people are considered not just recipients of charity, but active participants in the development process, whose rights must be respected. But the five-year results of the regional implementation of the International Madrid Plan of Action on Aging in the United Nations European Region of UN (UNECE UN) show that people aged 60 years and older demonstrate incredible work productivity and make a huge contribution to society, and with the right health care system in place, regular material support, social association and legal protection, both current and future generations of people around the world can receive «longevity dividends».

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MEDIA DISCUSSIONS ABOUT HOSPICE AND PALLIATIVE CARE IN UKRAINE SINCE THE BEGINNING OF THE WAR

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Palliative care is an approach that improves the quality of life of patients and their families facing the challenges of terminal illness by preventing and alleviating suffering through early detection, careful assessment and treatment of pain and other physical symptoms, and the provision of psychosocial and spiritual support [1]. Palliative patients are a particularly vulnerable category of patients who need special attention from the state and society, especially in conditions of social unrest (the COVID pandemic and war). Since the beginning of the full-scale war with the Russian Federation, hospices in the front-line and remote areas of Ukraine have continued their work, adapting to the new living conditions of both patients and staff. Analysis of recordings of discussions about palliative and hospice care (PHC) on the *Youtube* platform shows that their initiators are professional public organizations that care for palliative patients, scientists who study PHC organizers and the National Health Service of Ukraine (NHSU), which finances PHC under medical guarantee programs.

Thus, the analysis of the discussion, initiated by the former Minister of Health of Ukraine V. Knyazevich, allows us to understand how hospices and palliative care units in Ivano-Frankivsk, Kharkiv and Kyiv have been working in the conditions since the beginning of the war, how adaptation to new conditions took place, who is a participant in

the assistance palliative patients in Ukraine and abroad. Thus, the CNPE «Ivano-Frankivsk Regional Clinical Center of Palliative Care of the IF Regional Council» was established 25 years ago. Since the beginning of the full-scale war with the Russian Federation, the Ivano-Frankivsk hospice has not only not stopped its work, but also accepted additional patients. Individual patients were also invited to hospices in European countries (Poland, Germany, Finland). But most palliative patients are of limited mobility. Their transportation is a significant problem and the transportation of palliative patients took place with the participation of Ukrainian and foreign volunteers. However, most of the patients who remained in the departments of hospices and palliative hospices of multidisciplinary hospitals in Ivano-Frankivsk, Kharkiv, and Kyiv remained in their places and, together with the staff of these medical institutions, continue to hope that their institution will remain unscathed during the shelling. There is no technical possibility to transfer palliative patients to rooms protected from shelling. In connection with the close location of the city of Kharkiv from the border with the aggressor country, there is also no time to transfer patients to the bomb shelter. There is only one hope for protection of palliative medical facilities with anti-aircraft defense.

Some of the recordings we found of public discussions about PHC are timed to international days related to hospice and other types of medical care. For example, to the World Day of Hospice and Palliative Care, which is celebrated at the beginning of October every year [2]. On this day, WHO, professional public organizations, NHSU, the national Public Health Center, regional health centers, regional, city and district government administrations, health care departments, medical institutions that include palliative departments and wards, medical universities, medical information Internet-portals publish messages about PHC. They usually talk about what PHC is, how many patients in the world need for PHC, under what slogan of this day is celebrated in the world, what problems are being solved by states and regions to improve PHC, what help and support are needed for palliative patients and their relatives, how many patients take a palliative care, what are the legal grounds for providing such care, such as the organized work of mobile teams providing palliative care to patients at home.

Already in the autumn of 2021, before the war, more than 500 medical institutions provided PHC in Ukraine, and the NHSU paid more than UAH 800 million for these medical services. In hospice institutions and palliative departments, patients received pain medication and were placed in relatively comfortable conditions (in single or double wards with round-the-clock medical supervision). They carried out clinical laboratory and instrumental studies, oxygen therapy, fed, provided devices to facilitate the movement of patients with limited mobility (wheelchairs, walkers, sticks, crutches), carried out physical therapy, psychological rehabilitation for those who do not tolerate their difficult condition [3]. In order to successfully obtain funding for applications from medical institutions from the NHSU, the service held a series of public discussions to explain to customers the routes, algorithms for entering information in the Electronic Health Care System (eHealth), coding rules for ordered medical services, etc. [4]. NHSU noted that errors in filling out the documents for the application for funding can be the reason for the refusal to start funding or the reason for the delay in the continuation of funding, which can negatively affect the quality of PHC.

It is known that Ukraine still has a number of unsolved problems in the PHC organization [5, 6]. In the reform of the PHC organization, which Ukraine is continuing even in the war, the Ministry of Health of Ukraine focuses on the «best practices» of developed countries. Therefore, part of the video materials we found related to trainings

conducted by professional medical and social organizations, scientific and medical institutions, which shared such «best practices» [7].

Thus, the majority of public media discussions about PHC in Ukraine since the beginning of the war concern the adaptation of hospices, palliative care units, staff and patients to new living conditions. At the same time, there is a public discussion of the material and technical support of with the package financing of the NHSU in a professional environment. Public discussion of the problems of PHC providing contributes to a better understanding of the needs of patients whose lives are coming to an end, and also allows medical specialists to be more effective in the organization of medical care for this category of patients.

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THE EFFECT OF ECONOMIC CRISIS ON HEALTH SYSTEM IN LEBANON

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Introduction: The Republic of Lebanon is a democratic, parliamentary state located in the Middle East. It is a country of 10452 sq. km. The Lebanese population is estimated at approximately 5.2 million inhabitants (500 individuals per 1 sq. km) with the majority (85 %) living in urban regions, 38 % of whom are found in Mount Lebanon. There is a strong transition at the demographic level, with 25 % of the population below